

Supplement to the foot-rule problem

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The known area formula

$$F(\gamma) = \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha \cdot \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin(\frac{\gamma}{2} + \alpha) \cdot \sin(\gamma + \alpha)}$$

is valid for $\gamma \in [0^\circ, \min\{(180^\circ - \alpha), (360^\circ - 2\alpha)\}]$

Reason:

This area formula is based upon the area formula $F = ef : 2$ with the diagonals e and f of the kite. These diagonals must be positive.

Now we view the case:

$$\frac{\gamma}{2} + \alpha > 90^\circ$$

$$e = a \cdot \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

$$\frac{f}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{a}{\sin(180^\circ - \alpha - \frac{\gamma}{2})} = \frac{a}{\sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})}$$

For f we obtain:

$$f = \frac{a \cdot \sin \alpha}{\sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})}$$

With the area formula $F = ef:2$ we get:

$$F_2(\gamma) = \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})}$$

For $\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2} \rightarrow 180^\circ$ F_2 is increasing to +infinite.

We construct the differentiation:

$$F_2'(\gamma) = \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot [\cos(\frac{\gamma}{2}) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2}) - \sin(\frac{\gamma}{2}) \cdot \cos(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}]}{[\sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})]^2}$$

Necessary condition $F_2'(\gamma) = 0$:

$$\cos(\frac{\gamma}{2}) \cdot \sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2}) = \sin(\frac{\gamma}{2}) \cdot \cos(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})$$

$$\Rightarrow \tan(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2}) = \tan(\frac{\gamma}{2})$$

No solution for $\gamma > 2 \cdot (90^\circ - \alpha) = 180^\circ - 2\alpha$

There are no local extrema. F is increasing with γ .

If the kite has got a maximum length x, we can use the sine law:

$$\frac{x}{\sin(\frac{\gamma}{2})} = \frac{a}{\sin(180^\circ - \alpha - \frac{\gamma}{2})} = \frac{a}{\sin(\alpha + \frac{\gamma}{2})}$$

Then we get at x a maximum at the boundary. With known x we can conclude to gamma with the maximum area value.

Now we view the case of isosceles triangle:

$$\gamma + 2 \cdot \alpha = 180^\circ$$

$$\gamma = 180^\circ - 2\alpha$$

We insert $180^\circ - 2\alpha$ in both area formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} F(180^\circ - 2\alpha) &= \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha \cdot \sin(90^\circ - \alpha)}{\sin(90^\circ - \alpha + \alpha) \cdot \sin(180^\circ - 2\alpha + \alpha)} \\ &= \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha}{\sin \alpha} = a^2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha \end{aligned}$$

$$F_2(180^\circ - 2\alpha) = \frac{a^2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \sin(90^\circ - \alpha)}{\sin(\alpha + 90^\circ - \alpha)} = a^2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha$$

That means continuous continuation at $\gamma = 180 \text{ Grad} - 2 \text{ Alpha}$. This is clear with the figures, too.

Literature:

Harald Schröder „The foot-rule problem with numerical analysis“ ,2015, Zenodo